

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC STUDIES ON FERROUS COMPLEXES OF
QUINOLINE- AND PYRIDINE CARBOXYLIC ACIDS. PART I.
FERROUS QUINALDINATE SYSTEM

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The colour of the sparingly soluble ferrous complex with quinaldinic acid has been found to give its maximum intensity between pH 5.8 and 7, and the wave-length for maximum absorption at 500 $m\mu$. The intensity of the coloured solution increases in presence of an excess of KCN and to some extent with pyridine, both of which make the complex readily soluble. The colour system, obeys Beer's law even in the presence of KCN, maximum absorption with the latter lying at 515 $m\mu$.

The composition of the coloured system is given by $Fe(C_{10}H_8O_2N)_2$ with an instability constant, 3.63×10^{-6} .

Pyridine- and quinoline-carboxylic acids with a carboxyl group in the α -position to the nitrogen atom of the heterocyclic ring have long been known to exhibit intense yellow to red coloration with ferrous ion (Skraup, *Monatsh.*, 1886, 7, 210) in not too acid or alkaline solution. Utilisation of this colour reaction for the quantitative estimation of ferrous iron with quinaldinic acid was first made by Rây and Bose (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1933, 95, 400) in presence of potassium cyanide, which was found to intensify the colour to a great extent. Subsequently the method was critically studied and its usefulness confirmed by Majumdar and Sen (*this Journal*, 1950, 27, 245). Majumdar and Sen (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1953, 8, 369) also employed picolinic acid for the estimation of ferrous iron and determined the composition of the coloured complex by Job's method (Job, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928), and found that two molecules of the ligand were bound to each ferrous ion.

Wenger *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1952, 35, 396, 569) determined the dissociation constant of quinaldinic acid and the instability constant of the coloured complex of ferrous quinaldinate, assuming the composition of the complex as given by Rây and Bose (*loc. cit.*) from an analysis of the solid compound, namely $Fe(C_{10}H_8O_2N)_2 \cdot 5H_2O$. The value of this constant found is 2.6×10^{-6} .

Shimra *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1954, 78, I, 44) determined the composition of ferrous picolinate and quinaldinate in solution and came to the conclusion that both formed 1 : 3 complex in solution. As the results obtained by different workers for ferrous picolinate and quinaldinate complexes are somewhat contradictory, it has been considered worthwhile to reinvestigate the problem and to extend the study to other pyridine carboxylic acids which react with ferrous iron, affording characteristic coloured complexes.

It has now been confirmed that the composition of the ferrous quinaldinate in aqueous solution can be represented by the formula $Fe(C_{10}H_8O_2N)_2$, giving 1 : 2 complex, contrary to the finding of the Japanese workers (*loc. cit.*), but in agreement with Rây and Bose's results (*loc. cit.*) for the solid complex. The value of the instability constant 3.63×10^{-6} , as determined from the results of the present work, differs,

however, from that obtained by Wenger *et al.* (*loc. cit.*; 2.6×10^{-3}). This might be attributed to the difference in p_n values and the wave-lengths at which the measurements were made in the two cases. Wenger *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) found that the optical density of the solution remained more or less constant at or about p_n 3.6–4.7. They used a violet filter in a Specker-Hilger absorptiometer. In the present work it has been found that the maximum optical density of the solution lies between p_n 5.8 and 7 for 500 $m\mu$, which differs from the values given by Wenger *et al.*

The ferrous quinaldinate complex was found in two different coloured forms, dark red and blue-violet, by Rây and Bose (*loc. cit.*), differing in their solubility. This was ascribed by them to two different configurations of the complex, *cis* and *trans*.

The occurrence of a planar 4-covalent structure of ferrous iron is rather unusual, as in most of its complexes it shows an octahedral configuration. As the solid complex, given by Rây and Bose (*loc. cit.*), contains 5 molecules of water, it might be represented better by an octahedral configuration with two of the five molecules of water being bound to the iron atom in the complex zone.

The role of potassium cyanide in intensifying the colour of the solution of the ferrous quinaldinate complex possibly lies in the formation of a cyano-complex in solution in which one or two of the water molecules are replaced by the cyanogen group. This accounts for the increased solubility of ferrous quinaldinate in potassium cyanide solution, due to the formation of an anionic complex. The intensity of the colour of the ferrous complex increases with the increasing amount of potassium cyanide and then reaches a maximum and constant value beyond which no further change occurs, but the wave-length of absorption maximum (λ_{max}) remains unchanged. This is rather unusual. On keeping these ferrous quinaldinate solutions, a colour change occurs after about 72 hours, which increases with time and then decreases again, the solution finally becoming practically free from any characteristic colour. This is particularly noticeable with comparatively small or moderate amount of potassium cyanide present. The colour changes from pink-red to brownish pink and the absorption shifts towards the ultraviolet.

The addition of pyridine has practically the same effect as that of potassium cyanide, though to a smaller extent, upon the colour intensity. There is, however, one difference that unlike potassium cyanide, it does not lead to a maximum or constant absorption value, though the colour is intensified. The intensity of the colour continues to increase with the increasing amount of pyridine added. The absorption maximum of the solution is finally shifted towards the ultraviolet. The pyridine containing solutions of the coloured quinaldinate complex, however, on keeping for 2 to 3 days, deposit a dark chocolate crystalline product. This can, in fact, be readily obtained by adding moderate amount of pyridine to a strong solution of quinaldinic acid and ferrous salt. The compound on analysis was found to possess no definite composition, but gave values corresponding approximately to the formula of a mixed pyridine-substituted complex :

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The optical density measurements in the visible region in all these experiments were made with a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer, using glass cells having either 1 cm or 2 cm cross-section. For p_H measurements a Cambridge Bench type p_H -meter with glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was employed. The reagents used were all guaranteed quality reagent (Merck or B.D.H.). Reagent quality pyridine required for this work was always freshly distilled before use. All the reagents were used in aqueous solutions.

Ferrous quinaldinate, as already stated, though sparingly soluble, still gives a solution of sufficient concentration for colorimetric measurements. The solution yields a pink-red colour even when the metal is present in traces. The optical density of the solution, measured at 500 $m\mu$ between p_H 5.8 and 7, was found to obey Beer's law for ferrous ion concentration above 5 p.p.m., and gave a sensitivity of 0.036 γ ferrous ion per cm^2 (Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publishers, New York, p. 47). Twenty to thirty times the theoretical quantity of quinaldinic acid is required for the maximum colour development of ferrous quinaldinate. A quantity of potassium cyanide, at least 350 times that of ferrous iron present, is required for maximum intensification of the colour of the complex system. The coloured complex in the cyanide system is quite stable at room temperature and remains almost unchanged for about 24 hours. The sensitivity of the coloured cyanide system is almost four times greater than that of the pure ferrous quinaldinate system in solution.

Wave-length of Absorption Maximum and Influence of p_H on the Coloured System.

—In a small dry beaker, 10 c.c. of ferrous ammonium sulphate (50 p.p.m.) containing hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1%) was taken along with 10 c.c. of quinaldinic acid (1%) solution in water. The p_H of the mixture was adjusted approximately by the addition of a dilute sodium bicarbonate solution. The volume of the solution was then made up to 50 c.c. with distilled water and the p_H carefully determined by the p_H -meter. A number of solutions having different p_H values could thus be prepared.

A solution of p_H 6, which was quite strongly coloured, was employed for determining the absorption maximum which was found to lie at 500 $m\mu$. The optical densities of a number of solutions at different p_H were then measured at 500 $m\mu$ (Fig. 1). The maximum intensity of the coloured complex lies between p_H 5.8 and 7. There is little difference in λ_{max} though the intensity increases nearly 4 times with an excess of potassium cyanide.

It should be stated here that in every case the measurements of optical density were made immediately after the preparation of the solution in order to avoid the risk of any turbidity appearing from the separation of ferrous quinaldinate. The colour formation was instantaneous. The solutions of ferrous salt or of the reagent have little or no absorption at or about 500 $m\mu$. All the optical density measurements were made against water blank.

Beer's Law.—The coloured complex of ferrous quinaldinate with or without cyanide obeys Beer's law.

Influence of Cyanide and Pyridine Concentration.—The effect of the concentration of pyridine on the coloured system is shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 1
Influence of p_H .

Fe = 10 p.p.m. measured at 500 m μ .

FIG. 2
Effect of pyridine.

Ferrous amm. sulph. 50 p.p.m.
Fe containing $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ (1%),
10 c.c.; reagent 1% soln., 10 c.c.;
total volume 50 c.c.; cell, 1 cm;
515 m μ .

With an increasing quantity of potassium cyanide p_H may rise up to 9, and with pyridine, up to 7. That the increase of colour intensity produced by potassium cyanide or pyridine is not due to this increase in p_H is clear from the values obtained under the same condition, as given below.

Optical densities of three different solutions containing the same quantity of ferrous ammonium sulphate (10 p.p.m.), $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ (0.2%) and quinaldinic acid (0.2%) were measured at 500 m μ . One of these solutions contained pyridine, another contained KCN, in quantities sufficient to make the p_H value of the solutions the same (5.3) as that of the solution without KCN or pyridine. The following results were obtained. Cell used was of 1 cm.

	O. D.
I. With no KCN or pyridine	0.265
II. With pyridine	0.278
III. With KCN	0.540

From a concentrated solution of ferrous salt and quinaldinic acid, pyridine gives a dark chocolate crystalline product. This was prepared by adding a solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate (1 g. in 20 c.c. water) to a solution of 2.5 g. of quinaldinic acid in the minimum quantity of water and then treating the mixture with 5 c.c. of pyridine. The chocolate crystalline precipitate separating was filtered, washed and dried in a vacuum desiccator over CaCl_2 . {Found: Fe, 11.11; N, 8.95. $[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2 \cdot (\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{N})_2] \cdot 2[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{N}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ requires Fe, 19.82; N, 9.02%}.

Composition of the Coloured Complex of Ferrous Iron and Quinaldinic Acid.—The composition of the coloured complex in solution was determined spectrophotometrically by Job's method at p_H 5.99, with the use of sodium acetate—acetic acid buffer and in the presence of sufficient KNO_3 for maintaining a constant ionic strength. The optical density of the coloured solution gives a measure of the coloured complex in equilibrium. The values of measurements are shown in Fig. 3. The results show that the ratio of the coloured complex is 1 Fe : 2 acid.

FIG. 3

a. Ferrous ammonium sulphate (0.004M) containing $NH_2OH \cdot HCl$ (1%) x c.c. ; quinaldinic acid (0.004M) y c.c. ; KNO_3 (1M) 10 c.c. ; buffer 18 c.c. ; total volume 50 c.c. ; cell 2 cm ; 500 $m\mu$.

b. Ferrous ammonium sulphate (0.005M) containing $NH_2OH \cdot HCl$ (1%) x c.c. ; quinaldinic acid (0.005M) y c.c. ; 500 $m\mu$ and 550 $m\mu$; other conditions same as in (a).

Instability Constant of the Coloured Complex

The instability constant of the coloured complex can be derived from its dissociation in solution according to the equation :

$$K = \frac{[Fe^{2+}] \times [Q^-]^2}{[FeQ_2]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

(where QH = a molecule of quinaldinic acid and Q^- = a quinaldinate ion ; [] denotes concentration).

As the ionic strength of the solutions was maintained at a constant value by the addition of potassium nitrate and as the solutions of the reactants employed were very dilute, the activities of the various constituents may be considered to remain unchanged and may be substituted by molar concentrations. The values of $[\text{Fe}^{2+}]$, $[\text{Q}^-]$ and $[\text{FeQ}_2]$ in the equilibrium system can be calculated from the following equation :

$$[\text{Q}_t] = [\text{QH}] + [\text{Q}^-] + 2 [\text{FeQ}_2] \quad \dots (2)$$

$$K_a = \frac{[\text{Q}^-] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{QH}]} \quad \dots (3)$$

(where K_a = acid dissociation constant of QH)

$$[\text{Fe}_t] \text{ (total iron)} = [\text{Fe}^{2+}] + [\text{FeQ}_2] \quad \dots (4)$$

Now from the equations (2) and (3) the value of $[\text{Q}^-]$ can be calculated. Putting this value to equation (1) we get,

$$K_a = \frac{[\text{Fe}^{2+}]}{[\text{FeQ}_2]} \cdot \frac{K_a^2 \{ [\text{Q}_t] - 2 [\text{FeQ}_2] \}^2}{\{ K_a + [\text{H}^+] \}^2} \quad \dots (5)$$

$[\text{FeQ}_2]$ is known from optical density measurements. $[\text{Fe}_t]$ and $[\text{Q}_t]$ are known. $[\text{Fe}^{2+}]$ may be obtained from equation (4). $[\text{H}^+]$ is obtained from p_H measurement, and the value of K_a at 25° is 1.1×10^{-3} (Wenger *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

Table I (A, B) records the results of measurement of optical densities of the solutions studied.

TABLE I

A. Ferrous ammonium sulphate (0.002 M) containing $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ (1%) = x c.c. Quinaldinic acid (0.004 M) = y c.c. KNO_3 (1 M) solution = 10 c.c. Buffer (p_H 5.99) = 18 c.c. Total volume = 50 c.c. Cell-2 cm ; 500 $m\mu$. Temp. = 25° (room temp.).

B. Ferrous ammonium sulphate (0.002 M) containing $\text{NH}_2\text{OH.HCl}$ (1%) = x c.c. Quinaldinic acid (0.005 M) = y c.c. Other conditions are same as in A.

Fe-soln.	Quinaldinic acid.	O. D. at 500 $m\mu$.	Fe-soln.	Quinaldinic acid.	O. D. at 500 $m\mu$.
14 c.c.	6 c.c.	0.094	13 c.c.	7 c.c.	0.147
13	7	0.115	12	8	0.162
12	8	0.130	10 (d)	10	0.175
10 (a)	10	0.148	8 (e)	12	0.195
8 (b)	12	0.165	6 (f)	14	0.170
6 (c)	14	0.157	5	15	0.159

Now, from Table I, the values of K_c for a, b, c, d, e and f are calculated according to equation (5) and the results recorded in Table II, wherefrom the instability constant for the ferrous quinaldinate complex is found to be 3.63×10^{-6} .

TABLE II

No.	$K_a = 1.1 \times 10^{-5}$.		$[H^+] = 0.1023 \times 10^{-5}$.	
	$[Q_1^-]$.	$[FeQ_2]$.	$[Fe^{3+}]$.	K_c^- .
a	8.00×10^{-4}	4.82×10^{-5}	3.52×10^{-4}	3.03×10^{-6}
b	9.60×10^{-4}	5.36×10^{-5}	2.65×10^{-4}	3.02×10^{-6}
c	1.12×10^{-3}	5.11×10^{-5}	1.89×10^{-4}	3.21×10^{-6}
d	1.00×10^{-3}	5.69×10^{-5}	3.43×10^{-4}	3.96×10^{-6}
e	1.20×10^{-3}	6.35×10^{-5}	2.57×10^{-4}	3.90×10^{-6}
f	1.40×10^{-3}	5.53×10^{-5}	1.85×10^{-4}	4.66×10^{-6}

Hence K_c (mean) = 3.63×10^{-6} .

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